

Congregation of the Oratory

also known as “Oratorians”, “Phillipines”

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Entry tags: Rome, Roman Catholic, Religious Group

In 1575 a group of priests and men interested in religious life became the Congregation of the Oratory with the papal approval of Gregory XIII. In so doing they became one of many such groups of religious life founded in the Roman Catholic Church of the sixteenth century. Unlike many of these other orders, the Oratorians were not founded with a hierarchical structure enabled to organize a global order, but as a society of apostolic life. As such they were not bound to a central authority, but committed to a self-governing community. This presents a challenge for speaking about Oratorians as a group even in small chronological and geographic confines. Nevertheless, given that Oratorians drew inspiration from the original Roman Oratory inspired by Philip Neri, it is both critical and fundamental to understand Neri's life and the Oratory he founded in sixteenth-century Rome in order to make any generalizations about the Congregation of the Oratory. Neri, born a Florentine in 1515 Neri spent most of his adult life in Rome after a conversion experience that drew him into the practice of religion. He spent many of his early years in Rome as a committed layperson until he was ordained in 1551. In those years he began a ministry that included engaging with people on the streets of Rome about religion. Rigorous asceticism, a commitment to learning about ancient Christianity, and a profound commitment to Catholic aesthetics through the visual and musical arts characterized his devotional life. Over time he developed a following from laypeople as well as ordained religious that became the Oratory, distinct from the congregation. Here, the Oratory refers to program of spiritual exercises that Neri orchestrated and led in Rome. At first spontaneity was the defining feature of these spiritual meetings, but over time these meetings became arranged in a more consistent format and included brief sermons, historical lessons, and hymns. Philip focused most of his attention on developing and sustaining these spiritual conferences rather than on the government of the group in Rome and the other Oratories it inspired. In this respect, it is fruitful to compare him with Saint Ignatius, the founder of the Society of Jesus. While both oriented their life's work to the revitalization of Roman Catholicism, Ignatius exerted much of his emphasis in the governance of the Society he founded through his literary correspondence and perhaps more importantly by bequeathing his order with the Constitutions, which became the foundation for the Jesuit way of life. In contrast, the first Oratorian rule was only confirmed in 1612 by Paul V, seventeen years after Philip's death. In some ways this reflects Neri's reluctance to found a religious group at all. He preferred to encourage men to join other religious orders. Philip expected Oratorians to spend two hours at the oratory, preach or attend four sermons a day, preach peripatetically throughout the city, attend matins, and visit hospitals. Oratorian work was not limited to these activities. He also encouraged members of the Oratory to take part in catechizing children, and give individual spiritual direction. He was personally famous for seeing people in direction throughout the day. In addition, he commissioned some of his followers to take on specific tasks that he deemed critical. Perhaps the most significant of these assignments for the greater intellectual world of Early Modern Catholicism, if not Early Modern Europe, was the project he envisioned for Cesar Baronius: a complete history of the Church that became the *Annales ecclesiastici*. This multi volume work prioritized Neri's longstanding interest in Church History, which featured in both his personal devotional life and in the works of the Oratory. These efforts earned Neri and his Oratory a reputation for holiness and virtue, so much so that when Gregory XV raised Neri to sainthood alongside Teresa of Ávila, Ignatius Loyola, Francis Xavier, and Isidore the Farm Laborer, an aphorism echoed through the alleys of Rome saying: “we have canonized four Spaniards and one saint.” Neri's reputation for holiness was enhanced by his supposed thaumaturgic powers and his status as a holy mystic taken to frequent ecstatic or rapturous experiences, many of which happened while Neri meditated before a work of sacred art or heard sacred music. Neri

and the Oratorians were committed to the revitalization of Catholicism in its very heart, Rome. Their approach emphasized outreach to laypeople and pilgrims and highlighted many of the features that made Catholicism distinct, both a sensuous approach through preaching, music, arts, and architecture, and an emphasis on personal piety that emphasized intellectual stimulation and asceticism.

Date Range: 1575 CE - 1700 CE

Region: Italy and the Catholic Church

Region tags: Europe, Southern Europe, Holy See, Italy, Sicily, Rome

Italy and the surrounding region under the Catholic Church.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: *Instituta congregations oratorii S. Mariae in Vallicella de urbe a S. Phillipio Nerio fundatae* (Romae: Apud Iacobum Mascardum, 1630).
- Source 2: Louis Ponnelle and Louis Bordet, *St. Philip Neri and the Roman Society of His Times*, (London: Sheed and Ward, 1979)
- Source 3: Antonio Cistellini, *San Filippo Neri: l'Oratorio e la Congregation Oratoriana: Storia e Spiritualità* (Brescia: Morcelliana, 1989).

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.vallicella.org>
- Source 1 Description: The website for the Church of the Roman Oratory, Santa Maria in Vallicella.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.oratoriosanfilippo.org>
- Source 2 Description: Website of the procurator general of the Oratory.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Oratorians engaged widely with a variety of different religious groups. Primarily, the work of the first Oratorians put them in close contact with members of other religious orders. Furthermore, in the streets of Rome themselves they no doubt came into contact with Jews and other religious minorities. Overtime as they established Oratories throughout Europe and the world they came into contact with other religions throughout the globe.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Recent scholarship continually explores different types of religious competition. First, Oratorians were, like other religious orders, proselytizing both within Europe and elsewhere. They also endeavored to teach Catholic Christians about their faith. Finally, there was a certain type of competition between Catholic religious orders, if only informal, for prestige and status. This manifested itself in the construction and decoration of churches, but also in the attempts to canonize members of religious orders.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The Oratorians are not known to be a missionary order in the way Jesuits were and they did not develop intensive strategies of accommodation.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Like their contemporaries Oratorians were proselytizers, they aimed their efforts at conversion of souls either toward greater piety if they were already Catholic or to the Catholic faith if they were not.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Entering religious life in the Catholic tradition depended on discerning a vocation. The Oratorians are no exception. To belong to an Oratory an individual had to wish to be a part of it.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Oratorians accepted members from a variety of class backgrounds.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Here an important distinction must be drawn between the Oratory as a prayer group, which could include women (although the founder of the Oratory was suspect of having too much engagement with women), but prioritized men, and the Congregation of the Oratory which denotes the group of Clerks Regular founded to maintain the Oratory. Because this latter group was a congregation of priests it can only be composed of men.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Like other religious orders, Oratorians take vows, but unlike religious orders these vows are specific to an individual Oratory and not a larger group. Furthermore, as Oratorians typically become Roman Catholic priests they receive the sacrament of Holy Orders at their ordination.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the Oratory like other religious congregations engage in dialogue with non-Catholics considering conversion. Furthermore, they actively encourage men to consider joining religious life within an Oratory.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Only insofar as it is part of a Church wide program of evangelization, which is a longstanding aspect of the Christian and Catholic traditions.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: In the early modern period Oratorians, who belonged to a specific community based on their location would have interpreted their spiritual efforts as a type of missionary work. Oratorians, unlike other Catholic orders like Jesuits, Dominicans, or Franciscans, would not be sent away from their community for missionary work.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: In the early modern context the Oratorians depended on patronage. For the Oratorians in Rome, the major source of Patronage came from the papacy, which at that time, controlled the Papal States.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In religious life within the Catholic Church there are two possible forms of apostasy. First, leaving the Catholic religion for another religion. Second, leaving a religious congregation like the Oratorians for either another congregation or life as a layperson.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: How or if apostasy is prosecuted is highly contingent and depends on a case by case example. In the Roman Catholic context of the early modern period, certain forms of apostasy could result in excommunication. Furthermore, heretics, including apostates could be corporally punished. At the same time, Oratorian communities would not have meted out prosecution or punishment for apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: At present there are roughly 500 Oratorians throughout multiple Oratorian communities in the world. Given the decentralized nature of the Oratorians relative to other Catholic religious orders there are not very accurate numbers of how many Oratorians there were at any given period. This entry is based on the Oratorians in Italy and especially Rome in the Early Modern Period. With even this specificity it is hard to offer a number as the community at the Vallicella and other houses in Rome could vary in size year to year as members either died or joined the group. It must be noted that, in general and relative terms, Oratorian houses were not very large.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: In general, the number of Oratorians at any given point was not altogether very large. As a general rule a house should have four members with at least two priests and an additional two lay brothers.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Like other religious orders there is a hierarchy within the communities of the individual houses of the Oratory. Saint Philip Neri, the founder of the Oratory did not want to establish a centralized religious community. Therefore the hierarchies of each community varied slightly from house to house within Italy and throughout the world.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: There would be various roles in any given community with a type of hierarchy. The role of these leaders is complex as the example of the first leader Philip Neri indicates. The Oratorians only developed their first organizational structure two years after the foundation of the order in 1575.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Each Oratorian house enjoyed its own autonomy.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: There was not a single leader or rule; however, most of these houses were inspired by the personal example of Philip Neri and versions of the Institutes or Constitutions that came from the Roman house.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Individual religious communities would have a process for determining the hierarchy within their house.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Yes

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Religious leaders in the Oratorians have only organizational powers over their house. They are not able to make theological claims outside of the parameters of the Catholic Church.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Oratorians take vows including a vow of obedience, which maintains the hierarchy within an individual community. At the same time, the vow of obedience among Oratorians does not have the same significance it might among other religious orders established in the time period like the Jesuits, for example.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Oratorians, like all Catholics, use the Bible as their Sacred Scriptures. At the same time, they would have read other religious texts including works of theology, hagiography, and other devotional works.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: In the period in questions Catholics understood the Bible and its authors to be divinely inspired by the trinity. Nevertheless, all the books of the Bible were attributed to certain authors.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: It is crucial to note that the Bible, and especially the New Testament, tells the story of God revealing himself to man in the second person of the Trinity, Jesus Christ.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The authors of the biblical texts were considered to be non-divine, albeit saintly, human beings.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: While monumental religious architecture is not present it is important to note that the Oratorians, and indeed Philip Neri himself, cared deeply about the aesthetics of architecture and closely collaborated with architects and artists to build and decorate religious spaces, notably the Santa Maria in Vallicella.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Their buildings include churches and houses for the religious community.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: The first Oratorians in Rome worked assiduously to embellish their Church with decorations, mostly including iconographical works and other types of sacred art. After Philip Neri died, they commissioned works that depicted their saintly founder.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

- No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Ever since the Pauline distinction between flesh (sari) and spirit (pneuma) Catholic thought grappled with the duality between the body and the soul. The Oratorians certainly operated within this hyper Catholic cultural milieu where using and avoiding the body as a source of inspiration or temptation was a daily present reality.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Starting from the book of Genesis the Catholic tradition placed high value in the body as a created by God. At the same time, the spirit was and the mind were held in high esteem as higher than the body. In Catholic theology, it is the soul that lives on after death, until the Final Judgment at which time bodily resurrection will occur.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

- Yes [specify]: It is worth noting that the early modern period was one of the most notable periods of Christian mysticism. Mysticism presents a very interesting prism through which to study the relationship between the mind and body, because mystics describe their encounters with the divine through visions or other experiences as extra-sensory. Yet, for certain mystics, like Philip Neri the founder of the Oratorians, the mystical experience was born from sensory experience, such as viewing works of sacred art.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The actual physical location of heaven and hell, of course, could not be known. The thought of Dante was perhaps instructive through the early modern period imagining Hell as a type of subterranean abyss, and Heaven as a lofty place in the empyrean. For Dante Purgatory was a mountain whose peak held the Garden of Eden. These ideas were never fully clarified, yet it is clear from Catholic sermons and spiritual texts that the idea of Heaven being located in the Heavens and Hell within the earth permeated their thought.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: While mummification was not practiced, some efforts were made to preserve the body

of saints for display. In other cases bodies of saints were displayed without such attempts at preservation.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: It was a common practice to move corpses after being raised to saintly status such that the body could be displayed appropriately for veneration by the faithful.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: In some instances bodies, especially of holy people could be retreated for the purpose of display.

- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
 - No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

- No

Are grave goods present:

- No

Are formal burials present:

- Yes

Notes: Faithful Catholics were buried in consecrated ground. Individual religious orders had processes for how to bury their dead members. It was customary amongst many orders to bury their dead simply in a show of humility. At the same time, notable members of orders, especially those who displayed remarkable holiness might have their bodies marked such that if they were canonized they could be identified so that their bodies could be displayed.

- ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - Yes

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - No

Notes: While Catholic faithful might be buried with their families, this would be uncommon for members of religious orders.

- ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - Yes

Notes: Members of religious orders typically lived in a house adjacent to their main Church, and were often buried in a crypt somewhere in the house or church complex.

- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Catholic theology has long had a sophisticated system of angelology and demonology alongside its understanding of the Trinitarian Godhead. Beside the angels and demons, and the Trinity, Catholic theology and devotional practice also has a revered status for saints, that is, holy people, who have achieved blessed status in heaven after their death.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Only in the sense that the second person of the Trinity is Jesus Christ, who was, according to Christian theology, God incarnate.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: God is the King of Heaven and King of all creation, but not fused with a monarch that has earthly political power. At the end of time, Jesus Christ as second person of the Trinity is supposed to fulfill messianic prophecy and establish his authority on earth as supreme arbiter and judge of all people for the final judgment.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: N.B. during the period in question monarchs, including Catholic monarchs, made claim to preferred status by God, as specially anointed rulers by divine right.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The Catholic God is the Trinity three persons in one God (Father, Son, and Holy Spirit)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: In Catholic theology God is omniscient and omnipotent.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: In Catholic theology God is absolutely omniscient.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Through intercession God can work miracles in Catholic theology.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: God can work miracles on earth; however, the most important reward from God in Catholic theology is a place in heaven after death.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Strictly speaking the punishment for living a wicked life is supposed to be limited to eternal damnation in Hell, or temporary suffering in Purgatory; however the thought of some Catholic writers suggests that many believed at least at a popular level that God could and did punish the wicked on earth.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: God can respond to the intercessory prayers of saints to act in the world.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

Notes: Except in Biblical texts that either relate the emotional state of God the Father or Jesus Christ on earth the emotional state of God is not knowable.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The first commandment prohibits having any other Gods. This is known as the sin of idolatry. In Catholic theology it would be heresy.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer, sacraments, or mystical experience it is believed that God can make himself directly known to people.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Perhaps this is best considered as "mystical experience" rather than trance possession, although mystics describe trance-like states.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are present in the form of saints, deceased faithful, who are believed to be in heaven. They do not have a place in the physical world, but Catholics believe that they are mediators between people and God.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge and abilities of the blessed in heaven is really only an area of speculative theology and there would have been tremendous debate about the extent of their abilities. Answering any of these questions with certainty is not truly possible. On the whole, their ability to know about human affairs is perhaps akin to God's omniscience though in a less perfect sense.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: Through intercessory petitions with God saints can help effect miracles in this world.

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– No

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: Through intercessory petitions with God saints can help effect miracles in this world.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: In popular belief many people would maintain this, but this is an area of speculative theology that even Dante confuses. In his imagining of the Catholic afterlife, the deceased need to forget their past lives, and yet his saints maintain certain memories and awareness of life on earth. Ultimately, this is an area of speculative theology that Catholics do not have a firm answer on and Oratorians are no exception to this rule.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Both angels and demons are present in Catholic theology, and therefore Oratorians believe in them. While Catholics believe these are powerful beings the exact limits and extent of their powers is not and cannot be known.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Generally speaking, they cannot be seen; however, there are rare biblical instances in which angels or demons were seen. Some popular traditions also suggest that angels continued to work in the world as in the case of the Holy House of Loreto, which was supposedly transported by angels to Italy from Dalmatia.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The exact abilities and knowledge of angles and demons, like saints are not entirely knowable. They share to some degree in the knowledge and power of God, though the exact nature of this relationship is not knowable.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Like saints, angels can intercede for humans. Demons on the other hand can tempt humans to bad actions or thoughts.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Like saints, angels can intercede for humans. Demons on the other hand can tempt humans to bad actions or thoughts.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Only insofar as the second person of the Trinity, Jesus Christ, is, according to Catholic theology, fully human and fully divine.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Only insofar as Jesus Christ was physically seen during his life on earth.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Only insofar as Jesus Christ was physically felt during his life on earth.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Only insofar as Jesus Christ ate and drank on earth.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: There is in Catholic theology a hierarchy of supernatural beings including the angels and saints, but none of this is particular or peculiar to Oratorians.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Catholics are supposed to maintain periods of fasting and abstinence from

meat. This was true for Oratorians.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is proscribed by the fifth commandment, which Oratorians adhere to.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: The commandment not to kill was pervasive; however, Catholics defended just war doctrine and the execution of heretics in the early modern period.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Oratorians were male religious under a vow of chastity.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Oratorians would be precluded from all sexual activity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Laziness or sloth was a sin to be avoided particularly by religious.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Though sport and recreation were permitted to some degree in the Oratorian life, violence was to be avoided.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Notes: Giving alms and caring for the poor were part of the ministry of the Oratorians.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: Certain ascetic practices included shirking various standards of hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: In the Catholic tradition Jesus Christ is considered to be the awaited for Messiah, who at the end of time will return to earth and establish political dominion for the purpose of judging souls.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As priests and confessors the Oratorians would have preached sermons encouraging people to follow social Normas and would have heard confessions from those who did not. As part of the rite of confession they would also offer penances to the confessants.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: While this is a general characteristic virtue of Catholic thought it is important to note that religious are meant to be obedient to their religious superiors not their family after entering religious life.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: It must be noted that most saints from this period were Italian noblemen, who belonged to religious orders.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: It bears noting that Philip Neri, the founder of the Oratorians was, according to his contemporaries, remarkably joyful.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Oratorians, like other religious, and secular priests take vows of celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Complete sexual abstinence is a requirement.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Not only did Oratorians view fasting as a praiseworthy activity, they also follow all the appointed fasting rules of the Church during the Lenten season.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Oratorians would make every effort to be modest in their eating habits as befitting Catholic religious.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Still, self flagellation and other ascetic practices of self-mortification could be recommended

from confession or self-imposed to try to achieve greater piety. This would likely be encouraged moderately enough that painful bodily alterations and permanent scarring would not be a desirable result.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Of course, the stigmata (the wounds of Jesus Christ's passion), was highly prized by all Catholics. Still, there are not any famous Oratorians stigmatics.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Oratorians were encouraged to live abstemiously and poverty was a cherished ideal, but it was not the core principle of the Congregation as it was for the Franciscans or Capuchins for example.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The life of an Oratorian is entirely dependent on sacrifices of time for prayer. The Oratory itself, before the Congregation of the Oratory, referred to a prayer meeting. Outside of mass obligations Oratorians were expected to prepare and lead these prayerful groups which included sacred music, preaching, teaching, and biblical and religious reading.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Oratorians would follow the moral code of the Catholic church, avoiding mortal and venial sin and embracing virtues.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Oratorians would have been encouraged, and indeed expected to develop their own prayer life, they surely celebrated mass either together or in small groups, and they carried on spiritual conversation amongst themselves and at common meals.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As most of their life was oriented to religion, and nearly all of their deeds were planned around rituals it is difficult to say. They did not pray the office together like monks, so it would be challenging to ascribe time values between their prayerful gatherings.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This could vary very widely depending on the number of attendants at masses, or the number of people who came to pray with the Oratory. Oratorians like many other religious orders report very large numbers of people who attended their services, but in most cases there is no way of absolutely verifying that information. Suffice it to say that there were likely numerous occasions in which many people attended the Oratory, masses, or even spontaneous events with Oratorians.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Again it is difficult to say. There were surely multiple daily masses in the chapels around the Chiesa Nuova or other Oratorian Churches, and the prayer groups known as the Oratory would meet at least weekly, but possibly at other times as well. Furthermore, Oratorians had a

street ministry where they tried to engage with people spontaneously in the streets on religious matters as well.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Oratorians, like other Catholic writers were subject to Church censorship, and also had internal mechanisms of censorship. They also had a course of studies for men entering the order and achieving ordination as priests.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Oratorian life and ministries were ratified by Papal approval as were their Constitutions. Furthermore, Oratories like other religious had a formal process for ordaining members.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

Notes: Any dietary regulations that the Oratorians practiced would have been akin to those for any other Catholics, although they would have emphasized modesty in all things in their life including diet.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Like all Catholic religious Oratorians would have been tonsured at the time they were ordained into minor or major orders.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Oratorians, like other religious orders wore a distinct religious habit. Though their habit, like other congregations of clerks regular, was more akin to the priestly garb of Diocesan priests than monks or mendicants. The Oratorian habit is most distinct in its collar.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

Notes: Of course, Oratorians were expected to know and use Latin in the context or rituals, consistent with the regulations of the Council of Trent.

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Like the rest of the Catholic Church Oratorian priests are known as "Father" and they commonly referred to each other as "brothers."

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: This religious group in the period in question spread through and operated throughout Europe and other parts of the world in various states and political entities. Based on the sample region, the main focus is the Papal States.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Oratorians would partake in charitable efforts to help the poor, even if that was not their main priority.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The Congregation of the Oratory would only include religious professionals ministering to each other and laypeople who attended their churches and the Oratory.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: The Congregation of the Oratory has only male members.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: They would have and could have studied in institutions not controlled by the Oratory, but where there were respected and suitable Catholic theologians.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Oratorian bureaucracy was rather limited, because there was not a centralized organization by the design of their founder Philip Neri. Still each house had its own type of hierarchy.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Oratorians intercede with other Catholic religious orders and the Catholic Church and its bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Only insofar as there has been longstanding water management efforts in the Italian peninsula since the days of the Roman Empire.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Apart from the Papal efforts to manage crime in the Papal States.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Apart from the institutions established by the Papacy.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Apart from the laws that dominated the Papal States.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Papal States maintained an army as did other states in which the Oratorians had communities.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latin is the official language of the Catholic Church.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They would have used the Julio-Gregorian calendar, and the Roman calendar which marked important feast days.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Calendar would have been in use.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No